

Methods for quantitative assessment of seismic risk of linear structures (on the example of the Angren-Pop transport artery)

* Mansurov Azizjon Farkhod ugli

** Oripov Nozimjon Komilovich

Institute of Seismology of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

* Author for Correspondence: mansurovazizjon11@gmail.com

** Author for Correspondence: nozim.o.k92@gmail.com

Annotation

The article provides information on the methods of quantitative assessment of the seismic risk of the area where the Angren-Pop transport artery is located, and based on the results of the conducted scientific research, the last 10 years of data on the area under study is collected. Therefore, the engineering-geodynamic (dangerous-geological) processes associated with the Pamir-Hindukush earthquakes between 2012-2022 and the economic damage caused by them were assessed.

Keywords: Seismic risk, seismic vulnerability, tectonic disturbances, grunts.

Introduction

Transportation systems play a very important role in the world economy. They have a huge impact on economic growth and can be the main function of keeping it that way.

Transportation Types of transportation designed to move people and products by land transport (road and rail), river transport (sea and river), air and production lines. Land transport, i.e., road and railway transport networks, is carrying out cargo transportation by transport systems. Cars and trains are the most convenient transportation systems for transporting people and goods. For this, it is necessary to take measures to protect road and railway transport systems against products that may arise as a result of the effects of various natural disasters. These natural disasters (for example, earthquakes, floods, etc.) can have serious consequences due to damage to the transport infrastructure. Strong earthquakes can potentially damage transportation systems.

Data analysis.

Road transport has become the leading type of transport systems since the middle of the 20th century. The construction of new highways of the world's highways has increased and now has reached 27.8 million km, 1/2 of these roads are in the USA, India, Russia, Japan and Japan. It corresponds to China.. Road transport also ranks first in terms of the volume of passenger cargo, that is, it makes up 82% of the world. According to the data of the World Bank, about 80% of freight and

passenger transportation is carried out by road networks. In addition, annual ridership on nearby road networks will increase by 5 percent, and an additional 1.2 billion could be added to road networks by 2050, just like highway networks, any other transportation infrastructure, weak and can be damaged by various natural disasters.

Rail transport is second only to road transport in terms of freight volume, but is still an important form of land transport. In general, the world railway network was formed at the beginning of the 20th century, and its production now amounts to 13.2 million km.

Although there are railways in 140 countries of the world, more than 1/2 of the total adoption is in the ten most powerful countries: USA, Russia, Canada, India, China, Australia, Argentina, France, Germany and Brazil. European countries, in particular, are independent in terms of network density. On the basis of the above mentioned information, it can be said that taking measures to protect against natural disasters consists in producing the seismic risk that can be caused by an earthquake. Seismic risk is based on possible seismic risk in the area and the resulting secondary geological processes (slides, floods, avalanches, etc.) and construction objects (type of buildings and infrastructure, construction objects) assess the seismic vulnerability and determine the economic parameters of the objects (primary and market value of the object) and earthquake losses. Therefore, the study of natural and man-made factors affecting the stability of engineering objects and their evaluation is the basis of seismic risk today. Earthquakes pose a serious threat to road and rail systems around the world. For example, the Wenchuan earthquake of magnitude (M_s) 8.0 on May 12, 2008 is known to have caused 10.2 billion US dollars in economic damage to the transportation infrastructure. This resulted in a 12-day outage in the Baocheng transport line (UNCRD 2008) [5].

The earthquake that occurred in the eastern part of Japan on March 11, 2011 damaged 5600 sections of the national railway system. It took nearly a month to restore full rail connections (Edwards et al. 2015). Moderate earthquakes may not cause direct catastrophic damage, but when the peak seismic acceleration (PGA) reaches a certain level, trains must be stopped for safety reasons. In China alone, from 2012 to 2019, more than 88 earthquake-related railway disruptions were reported. About 10 percent of these deadly earthquakes caused serious damage to the railway system. These earthquakes caused significant damage to key components of bridges, overpasses, tunnels, and geotechnical structures, which in turn caused additional long-term damage to transportation road systems.

That is why research on mitigating and reducing the consequences of strong earthquakes is one of the urgent tasks of modern seismology. In areas of high seismic

risk, road and rail systems are constantly exposed to earthquakes and their associated secondary effects (e.g., landslides, fault initiation, ground subsidence etc.).

The area where the studied Angren-Pop transport artery is located is located in a complex relief area with various levels of deep cracks, fissures and tectonic disturbances. Rocks of various engineering-geological characteristics, chert rocks and deluvial soils are widespread in this area.

Figure 1. is a schematic map of the area where the Angren-Pop transport artery is located

Also in the area are reservoirs (Ohongaron, Rezaksoy), a railway tunnel with a length of 19.2 km and 2 highway tunnels with a total length of 2486 m. More than 21000 cars, trucks and special vehicles, as well as a number of passenger and freight trains, travel through this transport artery per day. On the basis of the above-mentioned information, works are being carried out to assess the seismic risk of roads and railways around the world (fig.1).

Seismic risk assessment is done by studying and analyzing the seismic risk assessment work of cars and railways around the world.

Research methodology.

Usually, risk is defined as the expected annual impact or loss (Winsemius et al. 2013), the following formula is presented, assuming the relationship between the probability or frequency of risk as a measure of the level of exposure to a certain asset. (Nekrasova et al. 2015): [6].

$$R = \frac{\sum_{e=1}^{T-EC} E(s, y_e) H(y_e) F(y_e)}{T} \quad (1)$$

Where R is the expected annual seismic risk ; E is the earthquake; T is the EC is the catalog of earthquakes in T years; E is the risk intensity level e ; S is the total

volume of mining work in the Transport Line area as well as the cost of Transportation line construction E(S, E) direct impact (Argyroudis et al., 2015) (Kappos et al., 2014) H - risk function; F - vulnerability function (Zuur et al., 2001) [6].

Analysis and results.

Based on the analysis of this formula, the data of the last 10 years on the territory of the territory of the Angren-Pop car and railway, which is being researched, were collected. So in this case, the engineering-Geodynamic (dangerous-geological) processes associated with the Pamir-Hindukush earthquakes of the period 2012-2022 and the economic damage caused by them were assessed.

Figure 2. Angren-Pop is dangerous that occurs in the transport artery geological processes

Table 1 economic damage caused by dangerous geological processes associated with the 2012-2022 Pamir-Hindukush earthquakes on the territory of the Angren-Pop railway[1,2,3,4].

№	Years	DGP number	Displacement volume m ³	1 m ³ DGP cleaning value, sum	exchange rate US \$ 1	Economic loss (in US dollars)
1	2012	3	65060	5700	1890,11	196201
2	2013	6	555	5700	2093,83	1535
3	2014	6	80585	5700	2312,81	198605
4	2015	9	4347	5700	2617,105	9468
5	2016	3	5200	13002	3023,975	22358
6	2017	16	156390	13002	5140	395600
7	2018	5	720	9021	8069	805
8	2019	4	881	25875	8851	2576
9	2022	3	5700	32819	11151,79	16775
General		55	319 438			843 921,9

This table shows that the economic damage caused by the dangerous-geological processes associated with the 2012-2022 Pamir-Hindukush earthquakes in the Angren-Pop railway area was US \$ 843 921,9.

Table 2. Economic damage caused by dangerous geological processes associated with the 2012-2022 Pamir-Hindukush earthquakes in the Angren-Pop Highway area [1,2,3,4].

№	Years	DGP number	Displacement volume m ³	1 m ³ DGP cleaning value, sum	exchange rate US \$ 1	Economic loss (in US dollars)
1	2012	12	4143	5700	1890,11	12494
2	2013	15	622624	5700	2093,83	1694968
3	2014	10	12106	5700	2312,81	29836
4	2015	9	381	5700	2617,105	830
5	2016	7	18210	13002	3023,975	78296
6	2017	4	16700	13002	5140	42244
7	2018	6	3210	9021	8069	3589
8	2019	5	65630	8066	8851	59809
9	2021	5	1240	14985	10643,33	1746
10	2022	4	3880	8200	11151,79	3176
General		77	748 124			1 926 987

And in the Angren-Pop Highway area, economic damage caused by the dangerous-geological processes associated with the 2012-2022 Pamir-Hindukush earthquakes amounted to us \$ 1 926 987.

It is very important not only to know the amount of economic damage caused by dangerous-geological processes associated with earthquakes of the above-mentioned years, but also to know the seismic vulnerability functions of the area under study.

Seismic vulnerability functions are a key element in seismic risk assessment; it is described by associating a given seismic intensity level with the probability of reaching or exceeding a given level of damage. Various methods such as empirical, analytical, evaluation, and hybrid can be used to create the seismic vulnerability function

Empirical method. In this way, seismic vulnerability functions rely on post-earthquake casualties and damage statistics. The reliability of the results largely depends on the completeness and diversity of empirical data collected on earthquakes in the area. In addition, seismic vulnerability functions can have large variations due to differences in data sets such as the amount of damage after the observed earthquake as well as the number of areas affected by the earthquake, the typology of road assets, and the earthquake range [6].

Analytical method. Analytic functions of weakness, mainly the basis of structural models Expert evaluation method. Based on the professional experience and opinions of experts, several functions of vulnerability are created. This method is easy and quick to obtain, but the reliability of the results is lower than other methods, because this method is not based on experimental data, but only on accumulated knowledge and experience. For example, Winter and other experts have determined the probability of road closures due to varying amounts of damage to roads that may be at risk of landslides through vulnerability functions created based on their knowledge and experience. In addition, the HAZUS methodology includes vulnerability models based on a combination of expert observations and empirical evidence from past earthquakes [6].

Hybrid method. uses a variety of approaches to integrate analytical, observational, and evaluative data. This approach can be useful for calibrating analytical results with experimental or empirical data. From this point of view, it is possible to reduce the amount of computation and increase the reliability of the vulnerability model. In addition, the hybrid method can be more effective than other methods because it combines different data sources, which makes it easier to create a vulnerability function and allows to reduce the error of other methods. In addition, it allows the creation of a vulnerability function taking into account all types of uncertainties.

Equations to generate vulnerability functions

The uncertainty in the vulnerability functions is related to the unpredictable variation of the seismic intensity indicators caused by various ground motions due to the notex movement of the roads under seismic influence. For example, the carrying capacity of road infrastructure does not change over time, but the carrying capacity of this infrastructure is uncertain during and after an earthquake. Vulnerability functions are usually described by a log-normal probability distribution as shown in equation (1) [6].

$$P_f(ds) \geq ds_i = \phi \left[\frac{1}{\beta_{tot}} \times \ln\left(\frac{s}{S_{mi}}\right) \right] \quad (2)$$

where (Pf) is the probability of reaching or exceeding a certain damage condition (ds_i), (φ) is the standard probability function, (S_{mi}) is the average limit of the parameter s earthquakes (for example, peak acceleration-PGA), the i-th damage condition and (btot) is the common normal standard deviation [6].

Figure. 3 The generated failure fragility curve of train services. PGA
peak ground acceleration

Summary

In conclusion, in order to develop measures to protect against possible losses caused by earthquakes today, this study aims to develop methods for quantitative assessment of the seismic risk of the area where the Angren-Pop transport artery is located and to put it into practice. The developed methods rapid development of dangerous geological processes associated with earthquakes will cause serious damage to the road and railway system, as well as the danger that may arise during the transportation of people and products by cars and trains, causing serious damage to people's lives Also, damage to transported products or loss of time affecting the movement of cars and freight trains, and this lost time will cause serious economic damage to production enterprises.

List of used literature

1. Yodgorov Sh.I., Mansurov A.F., Ergashev Z.Z., Khusomiddinov A.S. Report "Quantitative estimation of the seismic risk territory of the roads and railways (and the primary transport artery of Angren-Pop)." Pp-6-8.
2. Kodirov O., Suvonov Yu., Niyazov R.A., Erkabaev S. Provedenie monitoringa opasnyx geologicheskikh protsesov v gornyx i predgornyx zonax Akhangaranskogo rayon Tashkentskoy oblasti. (report Angrenskoy SS for 2012-2015). Pp -143-153.
3. Kodirov O., Suvonov Yu., Niyazov R.A., Erkabaev S. Provedenie monitoringa opasnyx geologicheskikh protsesov v gornyx i predgornyx zonax Akhangaranskogo rayon Tashkentskoy oblasti. (report Angrenskoy MS for 2015-2017). Pp -142-153.

4. Suvonov Yu., Khatamov ShS., Niyazov RA. Provedenie monitoringa opasnyx geologicheskikh protsesov v gornyx i predgornyx zonax Akhangaranskogo rayon Tashkentskoy oblasti. (report Angrenskoy SS for 2017-2020). Pp -139-152.

5. Suvonov Yu., Yusupov Khatamov, Sh. (report Angrenskoy MS for 2020-2022). Pp -148-157.

6. El-Maissi, A.M.; Argyroudis, S.A.; Nazri, F.M. Seismic Vulnerability Assessment Methodologies for Roadway Assets and Networks: A State-of-the-Art Review. *Sustainability* 2021, 13, 61. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13010061>

7. Zhu, W., Liu, K., Wang, M. et al. Seismic Risk Assessment of the Railway Network of China's Mainland. *Int J Disaster Risk Sci* 11, 452–465 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13753-020-00292-9> Pp-453-456.

8. Mohammadi, M.; Mosleh, A.; Razzaghi, M.S.; Alves Costa, P.; Calçada, R. Probabilistic Seismic Safety Assessment of Railway Embankments. *Appl. Sci.* 2023, 13, 598. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app13010598>